

A Study on the Current Situation and Outlook of the Development of Artificial Intelligence Based on the Idea of a Strong Science and Technology Nation

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ABSTRACT

As an important part of the strategy of strengthening the country through science and technology, artificial intelligence (AI) has gradually become an important engine to promote economic growth and social progress. This time, under the real social background, it proposes the research on the current situation and outlook of AI development. Briefly describe the connotation and characteristics of AI, and analyze the current development of AI from three aspects: data privacy and security mechanism, technical ethics and prejudice, employment structure and talent shortage impact. According to the above problems, we should formulate a series of strategies to make breakthroughs in core technologies and self control, enable the transformation and upgrading of traditional industries, strengthen the functional system and governance capabilities, build a multi-level AI talent model and improve the AI ethics and law system, and look forward to gradually breaking the bottleneck of data processing, providing more abundant and high-quality data resources for AI training, promote more innovative applications and business models, and achieve multi-directional innovation integration.

Keywords: Science and technology power; Ideological fusion; Artificial intelligence; Current situation analysis; Intelligent development; Data conversion.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI), as an important driving force for a new round of technological revolution and industrial transformation, has gradually become the focus of global attention. From the beginning, it has experienced multiple iterations and upgrades from symbolism, connectionism to evolutionism, and gradually formed a huge technical system ^[1] including machine learning, deep learning, natural language processing, computer vision, etc. The breakthrough and integration of technologies in multi industry fields not only promote the in-depth research of AI theory, but also promote the wide application of AI in many fields such as health care, finance, education, transportation, etc. However, in the process of development, people gradually realize that the development of artificial intelligence technology is not smooth. While promoting its wide application, it is also facing a series of challenges such as data privacy and security issues, algorithm bias and fairness, automation and employment impact ^[2]. These challenges are not only related to the progress and improvement of technology itself, but also related to complex issues at multiple levels such as ethics, law and society. Therefore, the research on the current situation and prospect of AI development based on the idea of strengthening the country through science and technology is proposed. Based on the current development environment, AI technology will continue to develop in the direction of more intelligence, autonomy and humanity ^[3]. With the continuous progress of technology and the continuous expansion of application scenarios, AI will also be deeply integrated with IoT, big data, cloud computing and other new generation information technologies to form a more flexible and changeable innovative development model and jointly promote the vigorous development of the digital economy. Further cultivate AI enterprises and industrial clusters with international competitiveness to achieve top-level design and strategic deployment.

1 A BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE CONNOTATIONS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

As a branch of computer science, artificial intelligence (AI) aims to simulate, extend and expand the theory, method, technology and application system of human intelligence. Its core is to enable machines to have the ability of perception, learning, reasoning, decision-making and self correction similar to human beings, so that they can complete complex tasks and even surpass human intelligence level ^[4] in some fields. The characteristics of AI are mainly reflected in the following aspects: first, intelligence. AI system can acquire knowledge independently, process and analyze data through algorithms, realize understanding and adaptation to the environment, and show some intelligent behavior. Learning is a key comprehensive feature of AI, including supervised learning, unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning and other ways to enable AI to optimize its performance in constant trial and error ^[5]. AI system can automatically adjust the strategy according to the changes of external environment or internal state, showing a high degree of flexibility and adaptability to cope with complex and changeable task requirements, reflecting its own adaptability. In addition, in terms of big data processing, complex computing, etc., AI can often show a speed and efficiency far beyond human beings, accelerate problem solving and decision-making, and has strong efficiency ^[6]. It integrates the knowledge and technology of mathematics, computer science, psychology, philosophy and other disciplines, and reflects a high degree of interdisciplinary ^[7].

2 Analysis of the current state of development of artificial intelligence

2.1 Data privacy and security mechanisms

With the rapid development of AI, data privacy and security issues are surging like an undercurrent, becoming more urgent and complex. In the process of development, data privacy and security mechanisms complement each other to form a more complete development model ^[8]. However, this trend has also increased the sensitivity of the collection, storage, processing and use of personal information, making data privacy a focus of attention of the whole society. The intelligent recommendation system provides users with personalized service experience by analyzing users' browsing history, purchase records and other sensitive information; Facial recognition technology shows great potential in security, payment and other fields, but also exposes personal biometric information to risk ^[9]. Such applications mainly rely on the flow and exchange of massive data, while data leakage, abuse and even illegal transactions occur frequently, which not only infringe the privacy of users, but also may cause a series of chain reactions such as identity theft and property loss, seriously damaging social trust and stability ^[10]. More seriously, the security of AI system cannot be ignored. Hackers may use system vulnerabilities or security flaws to steal sensitive data, tamper with algorithm logic, or even control the entire system, resulting in data leakage, system paralysis, or even more serious consequences, and burying security risks.

2.2 Ethics of technology and bias

The decision-making mechanism of artificial intelligence technology is deeply rooted in sophisticated algorithms and huge data analysis. This feature has brought unprecedented convenience and efficiency to daily life, but also quietly triggered a profound discussion of technical ethics and prejudice ^[11]. First, the decision-making of AI system does not exist in isolation, but is a direct product of training data. If these data are mixed with prejudice or discriminatory elements in the process of collection, annotation or collation, AI will inherit these problems when processing data, which will lead to errors in its decision-making results, and virtually aggravate the instability of AI application ^[12]. The specific influencing factors are shown in Figure 1:

Fig. 1 Graphical representation of factors associated with ethics of technology and prejudice

Figure 1 is mainly an analysis of the factors associated with technological ethics and prejudice. The instability of data sources makes it more difficult to ensure the diversity and fairness of data, which is not conducive to subsequent development and innovation. On the other hand, the "black box" characteristic of AI decision-making, that is, the lack of transparency and interpretability, has become a major obstacle to public trust ^[13]. It is difficult for users to see the complex operation logic and decision-making path inside the AI system during application, so they often have doubts about the fairness and rationality of its decision-making results. This not only limits the application of AI technology in some key areas, but also hinders the development and popularization of technology, lacking transparency and interpretability.

2.3 Employment structure and talent shortage impact

With the rapid development of artificial intelligence, the tension between traditional industries and emerging fields is increasingly significant. The wide application of AI technology is like a double-edged sword. Its efficient and accurate characteristics have greatly improved the production efficiency, but at the same time, it also makes the traditional jobs that rely on repetitive and low skilled labor face unprecedented replacement pressure. From assembly line workers in the manufacturing industry to tellers in the banking industry, and then to salesmen in the retail industry, these posts are undergoing unprecedented

changes. Unemployment risks are rising quietly, bringing serious challenges to the social and economic [14]. In addition, AI technology has also spawned many new jobs and career paths. For example, data scientists, machine learning engineers, AI ethics consultants, etc., require practitioners not only to have profound professional knowledge and skills, but also to have innovative thinking and interdisciplinary ability to adapt to the rapidly changing technological environment [15]. However, the current talent market is generally faced with talents shortage, can not satisfy emerging jobs requirements, further exacerbating the structural contradiction of the employment market. See Table 1 for specific contradictions:

Table 1 Analysis of Artificial Intelligence Technology and Employment Structure Talent Shortage Points of Contradiction

Contradiction point	Illustrate
Technology overcomes contradictions	Technological barriers to integrated storage and external limitations
Crossing hierarchical contradictions	Technological monopoly, inability to deepen development at the technological level
Contradictions in Technological Innovation	The direction and goals of innovation are unclear, and there are limitations of traditional technology
Contradictions in job scheduling	The disharmony between job demands and market trends

Table 1 is mainly an analysis and practical comparison of the contradictory points of artificial intelligence technology and employment structure and talent shortage. It has a hidden impact on the employment structure and talent shortage, but it is long-term and continuous, in such a background, if not timely adjusted and reformed, it will also cause uncontrollable impacts on the society, enterprises, markets, etc., resulting in the decline of the economy and slow development.

3 A STUDY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OUTLOOK OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE UNDER THE IDEA OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL POWER

3.1 Breakthroughs in core technologies and autonomous control

Under the guidance of the thought of strengthening the country through science and technology, breakthroughs in AI core technologies and self control become the key to development. In terms of in-depth learning, it is strive to make a breakthrough in complex task processing, minimize dependence on foreign technology, and achieve autonomous and controllable training and reasoning process. This not only improves the response speed of AI system, but also provides a stronger guarantee for data security and privacy protection. The field of natural language processing focuses on key technologies such as semantic understanding, emotion analysis, machine translation, and strives to achieve more intelligent and accurate human-computer interaction. Through the construction of a large-scale corpus and advanced pre training model, the gap with the international advanced level will be gradually narrowed, and the application mechanism and practice structure will be improved. In computer vision, image recognition, video analysis, 3D reconstruction, etc. need to be integrated to promote the wide application of AI in intelligent manufacturing, smart cities, automatic driving and other fields. Through independent research and development of high-performance image sensors and intelligent processing chips, the whole chain from data acquisition to processing and analysis can be controlled independently, increasing the controllability of AI for systems in various fields.

3.2 Enabling the transformation and upgrading of traditional industries

Under the guidance of this paper, AI is enabling the transformation and upgrading of traditional industries at an unprecedented speed, and injecting strong impetus into the comprehensive development of the economy and society. First, it improves the efficiency and accuracy of traditional industries through intelligent and automated production. In the manufacturing industry, AI technology is widely used in intelligent manufacturing, intelligent detection and other links, which not only reduces human costs, but also significantly improves product quality and production efficiency. Through data analysis and prediction, enterprises can more accurately grasp market demand, achieve customized and flexible production, and thus enhance market competitiveness. Secondly, the application of AI in the service industry is also increasingly widespread. In retail, finance, medical and other fields, AI technology has improved service quality and user experience through intelligent customer service, intelligent risk control, intelligent diagnosis and other means.

At the same time, precision marketing and personalized recommendation based on big data help enterprises better understand user needs, optimize products and services, and achieve innovation in business models. More importantly, the enabling role of AI is not only reflected in the specific production and service links, but also in promoting the upgrading and restructuring of the entire industrial chain. By building an AI based industrial chain collaboration platform, enterprises can realize resource sharing, information exchange, and accelerate technological innovation and achievement transformation. This will help break down industry barriers, promote cross-border integration, and form a new industrial ecology. The specific transformation and upgrading process is shown in Figure 2:

Fig. 2 A graphical representation of the process of transformation and upgrading of traditional industries enabled by AI technology

Figure 2 mainly shows the design and practical implementation of the transformation and upgrading process of traditional industries empowered by artificial intelligence technology. The transformation of traditional industries, to a certain extent, further expands the scope of its development, clarifies the corresponding direction, and promotes the high-quality under the guidance of the strategic thought of science and technology power to realize the science and technology power.

3.3 Strengthening functional systems and governance capacity

AI has significantly enhanced the decision-making ability of governments and public institutions through big data analysis and intelligent decision support systems. The integration of this technology can quickly process massive data, identify potential trends and risks, and provide scientific basis for policy formulation, which is more accurate and efficient, helps solve complex social problems and improve governance efficiency. In addition, the application of AI in the field of public services has promoted the innovation and optimization of service models. Intelligent customer service, online processing and other channels enable the public to enjoy a more convenient and efficient service experience. At the same time, AI technology can also help the government to achieve accurate allocation and efficient use of resources, improve the services, and meet the growing needs of the people for a better life. Application of AI in the field of regulation and law enforcement has enhanced the accuracy and deterrence of governance. Intelligent monitoring, data analysis and other means can help relevant departments and personnel to achieve real-time monitoring and early warning of market behavior, and timely discover and deal with violations. This intelligent supervision mode not only improves the efficiency of law enforcement, but also reduces the cost of law enforcement, which is conducive to maintaining market order and fairness and justice.

3.4 Build a multi-level AI talent model

Strengthening the training of basic theoretical research talents is the cornerstone of building a multi-level AI talent model. This requires higher education institutions to deepen the construction of AI discipline system and cultivate research talents with solid theoretical foundation of mathematics, computer science and AI. See Table 2 for specific system items:

Table 2 Multi level AI Talent Model Project Setting Table

Multi level AI talent model	Project Setting
Computer class	Computer Technology Innovation
Medical category	Intelligent medical equipment
Engineering	Improve the informatization of engineering mechanisms
Architecture category	Architectural Drawing and Resource Sharing
Electronic industry category	Integration of Electronic Communication and Technological Innovation

Table 2 is the setting of multi-level AI talent model project. The establishment of special funds and the construction of key laboratories can not only establish a complete learning mechanism, but also attract and train a group of top scholars with international vision and innovation ability to provide talent support for the original innovation of AI technology; Focus on application and development talents' training, and meet the urgent needs of the industry for AI technology faster through development and innovation. This includes adding AI related courses in vocational education and continuing education, cooperating with enterprises to carry out practical training projects, and cultivating compound talents who understand both technology and market. Encourage and support innovation and entrepreneurship, and provide talent guarantee for the rapid transformation and application of AI technology; Build an industrial practice talent system and promote the deep integration of AI technology in various industries. In the process of development, the enterprise strengthened internal training, improved employees' awareness and application ability of AI technology, established close cooperation with universities and research institutions, and jointly carried out technology research and development and talent training projects. Constantly promote the tempering of industrial practice and cultivate a group of AI experts who understand both technology and business and can solve practical problems.

3.5 Improve the AI ethical laws and regulations system

It is necessary to clarify the ethical boundaries of AI technology to improve the AI ethics regulation system. With the wide application of AI technology, its decision-making process and results may involve many ethical issues, such as privacy protection, algorithm bias, responsibility attribution, etc. Therefore, it is the foundation to ensure the healthy development of AI technology by formulating clear ethical standards and regulations and defining the scope and restrictions of AI technology. At present, under different environments and requirements, it is necessary to first improve the regulatory mechanism to ensure the effective implementation of AI ethics regulations. Establish a sound regulatory system, clarify the responsibilities and authorities, and strengthen the supervision of AI technology R&D, application and services. In addition, with the fluctuation of demand, more punishment should be given to illegal behaviors to form an effective deterrent effect and ensure the authority and seriousness of AI ethics laws and regulations. It is also crucial to strengthen public education and publicity, and improve the awareness and participation of society on AI ethics. In the process of development, popularize AI ethical knowledge, carry out relevant educational activities and other ways to improve the public's awareness and understanding of AI technology, and enhance their attention and participation in AI ethical issues. This will help to form an AI ethical governance pattern with the participation of the whole society and promote the healthy development of AI technology.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the above is a study on the current situation and outlook of the development of artificial intelligence based on the idea of a strong scientific and technological country. As the core driving force, AI plays an important role in various fields. This time, it is measured and analyzed from multiple perspectives, and more original and leading scientific and technological achievements are used as examples for comparison, so as to highlight the application effect of AI. In addition, it also needs to bring much attention to and solve the ethical, legal and social issues that associated with the technology, so as to ensure the healthy development and wide application of AI technology, and to jointly promote the innovation and development of AI technology, and to contribute to the strengthening of the scientific and technological power of the society.

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